

Bandwidth Extension of PCB Rogowski Coils Using Distributed Damping

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Abstract—PCB Rogowski coils are commonly used sensors for wide-band current measurements due to their low cost, high bandwidth potential and ease of integration into existing systems. However, their performance is currently constrained by a trade-off between their maximum frequency of operation and their low-frequency sensitivity. In this paper, a novel distributed damping network capable of significantly extending the bandwidth of PCB Rogowski coils with minimal impact on their low-frequency mutual inductance is proposed. A complete modeling framework and two numerical methods that implement it with different levels of fidelity are presented. These methods accurately predict the high-frequency response of a sensor equipped with the proposed network under realistic measurement conditions, and achieve nearly an order-of-magnitude speedup compared to existing full-wave solvers. Using a custom test fixture, alongside the fabrication of a wide array of sensors implementing the proposed networks, the theoretical predictions of the models are validated experimentally. A fivefold increase in the -3 dB bandwidth of the fabricated PCB Rogowski coils is demonstrated, with negligible impact on their low-frequency sensitivity and at the cost of only two additional resistors per turn.

Index Terms—Current measurements; distributed-element model; partial mutual inductance; PCB Rogowski coils.

I. INTRODUCTION

ROGOWSKI coils (RCs) implemented using printed circuit boards (PCBs) [1], [2] are widely used sensors for the measurement of high-frequency currents up into the hundreds of megahertz range. Due to their low cost, ease of system integration and high customizability, they have been employed in a wide variety of applications that span from the measurement of switching currents in power converters [3] to lightning strike currents in aircraft [4] and clamp-on probes for general electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) work

[5]. A PCB RC is typically constructed as a rectangular toroid using vias for the vertical sidewalls of the structure which are connected together with much longer horizontal PCB traces. Additionally, it is usually necessary to shield these coils, both to suppress capacitive coupling from the primary conductor or others nearby and to properly establish the high-frequency propagation constants of the structure irrespective of changing environmental conditions [6]–[8].

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Previous works have demonstrated that conventional helically wound RC sensors can be represented as a transmission line (TL) subject to a distributed excitation that accounts for the voltages induced in the coil by the primary current [9]–[11]. In these models, the resonances of the probe originate from the destructive interference of many different voltage standing waves. These waves may be created by reflections at the terminations (typically, a short-circuit at one end and a terminating resistor R_L at the other) or, more fundamentally, may arise as the spatially distributed induced voltage reaches the output with different propagation delays. Furthermore, because the latter mechanism depends on the exact geometrical distribution of the induced voltage, both the frequency and shape of these resonances exhibit a strong dependence on the geometry of the primary conductor [12], requiring a conservative bandwidth margin to accommodate

arbitrary primary current path geometries. Typically, the sensor's usable bandwidth is limited to frequencies below the first resonance, above which the output voltage is no longer proportional to the primary current.

Below this first resonant frequency, the response of the sensor to the current under measurement is derivative and proportional to its mutual inductance, M . A larger M therefore increases the output voltage of the sensor and reduces the relative impact of the integrator front-end noise; this is particularly important at the lowest frequencies of interest, where flicker noise can become significant [13]. Ultimately, the total output noise will determine the smallest current measurable by the sensor. However, PCB RC configurations that increase M collaterally shift the first resonance to a lower frequency [1]. For example, increasing the number of turns or the difference between the outer and the inner radius of the sensor increases the electrical length of the shielded trace that forms the coil and modifies its distributed parameters, which reduces the associated resonance frequencies.

This inherent trade-off between noise and bandwidth in PCB RCs has been discussed in preceding studies, and different solutions have been proposed. One alternative is to compensate the first resonance of the sensor using either an analog filter [14] or digitally in post-acquisition [15], [16]. This solution works well when the coil is fixed in a known position, particularly if its transfer impedance, Z_T (i.e. its output voltage per unit of primary current), can be measured directly in situ. However, it is unsuitable when the placement of the primary conductor relative to the RC is unknown, due to the aforementioned dependence of the resonances on the path of the primary current [12]. Another option reported in the literature is to divide the coil into multiple sections, integrate the output voltage of each section individually, and then sum the resulting signals [17]. Ideally, this segmentation preserves the low-frequency sensitivity of the original sensor, while the reduced length of each section increases the attainable bandwidth. Nonetheless, the bandwidth improvement achieved with this approach diminishes rapidly as the number of turns per section is reduced, for both PCB and helical implementations [18]. It is also possible to exploit the coil's intrinsic inductance in combination with a low terminating resistance R_L to produce a self-integrating response at higher frequencies. Introducing a zero in the integrator at the associated corner frequency compensates this behavior and relaxes the integrator's high-frequency design requirements. A first-order analysis shows that, for a perfectly uniform induced voltage distribution, resonances can be suppressed this way [9]. Unfortunately, a more detailed analysis shows that even small asymmetries in this distribution created by minor geometrical imperfections can cause significant resonant peaks to reappear [12], [19]. Furthermore, no equivalent analysis has been performed so far for PCB RCs.

In comparison to the previously discussed methods, which aimed to compensate or increase the frequency of the resonances, the inclusion of a distributed damping network around the coil has the ultimate objective of suppressing them as much as possible. This technique has previously been applied in various forms to conventional toroidal current

transformers with a magnetic core [20], [21], but to the best of the authors' knowledge no previous work exists that discusses its implementation in PCB RCs. Furthermore, previous applications of distributed damping have been justified either on the basis of empirical observations [20] or using models that represent the added loss as a distributed parameter along the sensor TL [21], without acknowledging that the damping elements themselves are lumped and connected only to discrete points on this TL. As a result, these models do not reliably predict the high-frequency limitations of this technique, and the parameter selection of the distributed damping network is still largely performed by trial-and-error.

To address these gaps, this paper proposes a distributed damping network specifically designed for PCB RCs, which significantly increases sensor bandwidth without noticeably altering low-frequency sensitivity. Furthermore, two dedicated numerical techniques are introduced to rapidly design and tune this network under realistic measurement conditions while accounting for the high-frequency propagation effects within the coil. These techniques allow the proposed network to be optimized and applied to existing PCB RCs with minimal experimental characterization. The accuracy of this modeling framework as a whole is then validated experimentally.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: In Section II, some modeling considerations applicable to all PCB RCs are given, and two numerical methods for implementing them with different degrees of detail and speed are presented. These allow for the analysis of the high-frequency effects associated with arbitrary primary current geometries and the efficient determination of optimum values of the distributed damping resistors, respectively. Subsequently, Section III describes the construction of some example PCB RCs alongside the high-frequency test-fixture employed to validate the proposed bandwidth extension method and associated numerical techniques. Finally, Section IV describes the application and subsequent experimental validation of these techniques to a wide range of test coils.

II. MODELING FRAMEWORK AND NUMERICAL METHODS

This section presents the basic considerations needed to accurately model the high-frequency behavior of PCB RCs, as well as how that behavior changes after adding the proposed distributed damping network. An intuitive explanation for the working principle of the latter is given, and it is shown how the complexity of the resulting structure rules out exact analytical solutions. For this reason, two different numerical techniques are presented, which are able to construct and solve an equivalent circuit of the sensor that captures its high-frequency response of interest.

Many of the conclusions reached by TL models of conventional, helical coils presented in Section I can be translated to PCB RCs, but for an accurate design of the distributed damping network their irregular via-and-trace geometry must be considered. As a guide for the discussion that follows, a 3D render of a typical sensor is shown in Fig. 2, which also illustrates the modeling choices made for each element of the structure. From a circuit perspective,

Fig. 1. Proposed equivalent circuit for the sensor incorporating the distributed damping network, where the sensor traces are represented by TLs (which for non-parallel primary conductors will need to incorporate a distributed voltage excitation) and the vias by lumped voltage sources. In a first approximation, both the parasitic components of the resistors and the partial self-inductance of the vias are neglected.

Fig. 2. 3D render of a typical current sensor with a section of the top shield removed for visualization purposes and all key elements marked. Note the two rings of equal-valued resistors connecting each successive inner and outer via that compose the proposed distributed damping network.

$$M_{p_{mn}} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \frac{1}{A_m A_n} \int_{V_m} \int_{V_n} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{t}}_m \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_n}{|\mathbf{r}_m - \mathbf{r}_n|} dV_m dV_n. \quad (1)$$

Because the numerator of the integrand in (1) contains a dot product, in the reference case of a perfectly straight primary conductor normal to the PCB plane (and thus parallel to the vias) induced voltages appear only on the inner and outer vias of the coil; the connecting traces are perpendicular to the primary conductor and therefore have zero partial mutual inductance. Further numerical calculations indicate that even for highly inclined or looping primary configurations the induced excitation remains predominantly concentrated in the vias; however, the contributions from voltages induced in the traces should still be included, since their different propagation delays can affect the high-frequency response and resonance shape.

Consider now the addition of the two resistor rings across each inner and outer via, as shown in Fig. 2. Rather than understanding them as externally added losses to some resonant structure, they can be interpreted as alternative current paths that allow the induced currents to reach the output with a much smaller propagation delay than if they had to traverse the much longer PCB traces. At low-frequencies, these resistors are expected to have a negligible effect on the output voltage because they are in parallel with the very low resistance of the connecting traces. However, at high-frequencies where the input impedance of these traces increases due to TL effects, they should provide a lower impedance alternative path for the induced current to reach the output. Remaining resonances are attributed to the short TL sections between adjacent damping resistors (much shorter than the complete sensor coil); at sufficiently high frequencies, the discrete nature of the loading allows these sections to exhibit local resonant modes.

the long, horizontal PCB traces should be modeled as TLs with an impressed distributed voltage per-unit-length (pul), which may vary along the line to represent a spatially distributed excitation. In contrast, the vias are much shorter, and do not exhibit transmission-time effects until much higher frequencies; furthermore, their capacitance is typically negligible [22] in the frequency range of interest. Thus, they can be modeled using a single lumped voltage source to account for the voltage induced therein.

This irregular geometry also strongly affects the distribution of induced voltages around the structure, which can be quantified using the concept of partial mutual inductance [23], [24]. By assuming a quasi-static regime and ignoring displacement currents, all induced voltage will appear across the structure in phase, and all phase differences at the output will originate exclusively from different propagation delays across the TLs. The static partial mutual inductance between two different volumes V_m and V_n , centered around \mathbf{r}_m and \mathbf{r}_n , with cross sections A_m and A_n and unit vectors in the direction of current flow $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_m$ and $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_n$ respectively is [25]:

By applying the considerations previously discussed, the structure represented in Fig. 2 can be reduced to an equivalent circuit like that shown in Fig. 1, where each of the TLs shown might include a distributed voltage varying over its length, depending on the path of the primary current. Since only coils with a uniform distribution of turns as well as with a constant trace-to-shield spacing are considered, their characteristic impedance Z_0 can be assumed constant. Finally, note that the connections of the damping resistors R_{damp} in Fig. 1 indicate that, physically, all connections are made in the same PCB layer.

The complexity of the circuit in Fig. 1 precludes a closed-form expression for the output transfer function, even for a fully centered, collinear primary conductor. To address this, two numerical techniques are introduced. The method in Section II-A computes Z_T for arbitrary primary-current paths and for any configuration of R_{damp} , providing the most general and accurate solution. However, its high complexity and non-negligible computational cost make iterative optimization of R_{damp} cumbersome. For this reason, Section II-B presents a second, optimization-oriented approach that evaluates the relative change in Z_T versus R_{damp} only for a centered primary.

A. Modeling of the high-frequency response for arbitrary primary geometries.

The objective of this method is to predict the high-frequency behavior of the sensor for different configurations of the distributed damping network while accounting for the possibly non-uniform distributed voltage excitation caused by an arbitrary primary current path. For all simulations, the structure of the network (i.e., one ring connecting the inner vias and another ring connecting the outer vias) and hence the equivalent circuit of the complete sensor is preserved, while the value of R_{damp} is swept until the flattest transfer function is found.

The only restriction placed on the primary current path is that it must be represented as a series of straight, one-dimensional current filaments; this is easily satisfied for typical use cases (such as when the probe is clamped around a wire) because curved trajectories can be approximated by straight segments. A preliminary electromagnetic simulation to determine the current distribution is only required for more complex primary fixtures [26] where the current is not known *a priori* or might vary with frequency due to the skin and proximity effects. The most important steps of the process are outlined in Fig. 3 and will be discussed below.

Fig. 3. Flowchart describing the complete simulation process to consider the effect of arbitrary primary current geometries on the high-frequency response of the sensor.

Existing TL models in commercial SPICE simulators cannot directly represent a spatially varying distributed series excitation. Therefore, the TLs used to model the PCB traces are discretized into segments of maximum length Δx , each corresponding to a LC ladder section in series with a voltage source (a VLC segment). The magnitude of the voltage source

is computed from the pul partial mutual inductance of that specific segment with respect to the primary current, $M'(l_{\text{seg}})$. An illustration of the process is shown in Fig. 4.

These discretizations must be fine enough to emulate the high-frequency response of the TL [27] and to capture fast spatial variations of the induced voltage; except for highly localized excitations, the first criteria is usually the most demanding. Since this study is limited to coils with a uniform Z_0 , the inductance L' and capacitance C' pul of the horizontal traces are constant, and thus the classical criterion for approximating a TL with discrete components can be employed to determine the needed Δx as a function of the maximum frequency of interest f_{max} [27]:

$$f_{\text{max}} \ll \frac{1}{10\Delta x \sqrt{L'C'}}, \quad (2)$$

which is typically verified by subsequently making small changes in Δx and ensuring that the output is insensitive to them, since it is otherwise not possible to know beforehand if the spatial variations in M' have been properly captured. These pul parameters can be calculated either using existing formulae or, alternatively, by measuring the total impedance of an identical sensor to the one under study whose distributed damping network has been removed.

Fig. 4. Representation of a section of a typical sensor comprising four turns and the inner and outer damping resistor rings. Traces on the upper and lower layers are shown in green and blue, respectively; the crosses indicate the vias connecting the two layers. The resistors shown in red are the distributed damping network. Each marked segment corresponds to a discrete VLC element. Vias are excluded from the segmentation process.

Secondly, the partial mutual inductance between each individual segment or via and the primary current is calculated. Analytical formulae for discrete, straight current filaments are available [28] and employed here. Due to the low thickness and width of the sensor traces, only a small error is introduced by this filamentary approximation, but in return a very significant speedup in simulation times is achieved in comparison to numerically solving (1).

Finally, a netlist containing a circuit like that shown in Fig. 1 but with all the TLs replaced by the corresponding number of VLC segments in series is obtained. The same program employed to calculate $M'(l_{\text{seg}})$ stores the resulting values and

automatically constructs the netlist with the correct syntax on a text file. This netlist can then be exported directly to the preferred SPICE solver to perform a swept frequency, small signal AC simulation and find Z_T . This last step is repeated for all desired values of R_{damp} ; the segmentation and calculation of partial mutual inductance need only be done once for each coil and primary current configuration.

The main advantage of this methodology in comparison to existing full-wave solvers, which naturally include the distributed excitation and propagation effects, is its speed. A single simulation capturing the first few resonances on a typical sensor takes approximately 3 minutes on a standard, consumer-grade laptop. In comparison, even without the distributed damping network, a full-wave simulation of the coil structure using OpenSEMBA's Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) implementation [29] in a multi-core server typically takes several hours. Thus, the speed advantage is sufficiently large to remain evident even when the proposed method is run on substantially less powerful hardware. This speedup is achieved by exploiting the known TL structure of the sensor and considering only the desired magnetic couplings.

When designing a distributed damping network, R_{damp} is swept over a wide range to identify an optimum value, often spanning roughly two orders of magnitude below and above the coil's Z_0 . As a result, even with the speedup achieved, runtimes of several minutes per netlist evaluation can still make iterative optimization cumbersome. Moreover, its complexity (both in the segmentation process and in the numerically accurate implementation of the complex partial mutual inductance formulae) can hinder the rapid and convenient design of new sensors. For this reason, the next section presents a fast method for exclusively determining the optimum value of R_{damp} .

B. Fast determination of optimal values for the distributed damping network.

As shown by the previous analysis, the resonances of conventional PCB RCs depend markedly on the distribution of induced voltages across the coil. The distributed damping network serves to propagate those induced voltages to the output with the minimum phase-shift difference between them, regardless of their origin within the structure. It follows that, if all these voltages reach the output in phase, they will be added there algebraically with no destructive interference. Thus, for a properly designed distributed damping network, the high-frequency response of the sensor loses, to first order, its dependence on the geometrical distribution of induced voltages, and hence on the inclination and eccentricity of the excitation current.

Therefore, if an optimal value of R_{damp} is found for the ideal case of an infinitely long primary current filament, collinear with the sensor axis (i.e., no inclination, no eccentricity) then the behavior of the sensor under more realistic primary current geometries will be similar, even if that is not the case for other values of R_{damp} which are not able to suppress as efficiently the propagation delays of the TLs of the coil. As can be seen from

Fig. 5, for this particular case the two main complexity sources of the method presented in Section II-A can be removed entirely.

Fig. 5. Flowchart describing the simplified simulation process for determining the optimum value of R_{damp} .

First, since all induced voltage is concentrated on the vias, the TLs do not need to be approximated using VLC segments, and instead can be described using standard lossless method of characteristics models [30], [31]. This not only removes the discretization step entirely, but also very significantly decreases simulation times, as these models have very few internal nodes, independently of TL length or maximum frequency of interest. Secondly, since the primary filament is perfectly centered and collinear to the coil, due to the radial symmetry of the structure all inner vias will have the same partial mutual inductance. The same holds true for the outer vias:

$$\begin{aligned} V_{\text{inner}_{1,2,\dots,n}} &= V_{\text{inner}} = j\omega M_{\text{inner}} I_p \\ V_{\text{outer}_{1,2,\dots,n}} &= V_{\text{outer}} = j\omega M_{\text{outer}} I_p. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Consider that the centered, collinear primary current filament has a length L , much longer than the vias height h and the outer radius of the coil r_{outer} (the radius where the outer vias are located). Then, existing expressions for parallel current filaments [32] can be approximated under both of these conditions to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\text{inner}} &\approx \frac{\mu_0}{2\pi} h \ln \frac{L}{r_{\text{inner}}} \\ M_{\text{outer}} &\approx \frac{\mu_0}{2\pi} h \ln \frac{L}{r_{\text{outer}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where r_{inner} is the inner radius of the coil (the radius where the inner vias are located). Furthermore, for finding the optimum value of R_{damp} (or general structure of the distributed damping network), only the relative flatness of each Z_T transfer function is of interest, rather than its absolute magnitude. They can thus be normalized to make calculation and presentation more convenient by setting:

$$\begin{aligned} V_{\text{inner,rel}} &= \frac{V_{\text{inner}}}{M_{\text{inner}} I_p} = j\omega \\ V_{\text{outer,rel}} &= \frac{V_{\text{outer}}}{M_{\text{inner}} I_p} = -j\omega \frac{\ln L - \ln r_{\text{outer}}}{\ln L - \ln r_{\text{inner}}} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

For typical coil designs, setting $L = 1$ m easily fulfills the necessary inequalities $L \gg h$, $L \gg r_{\text{outer}}$ and further simplifies (5). Note the minus sign in V_{outer} to account for the current flow in the outer vias being in the opposite direction to that in the inner vias. Using the default lossless TL models available in LTSpice, the equivalent circuit shown in Fig. 1 allows the simulation of over 200 values of R_{damp} per minute in a commercial laptop, highlighting the fast, iterative sensor design supported by this method.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this section, the experimental setup employed to validate the effectiveness of the proposed distributed damping network and the accuracy of the numerical methods outlined in Section II is described. Firstly, the test coils designed and manufactured for this purpose are addressed. Afterwards, the test fixture employed to generate the needed high-frequency calibration currents is characterized, and finally the subsequent de-embedding process is reported.

A. Coil assembly and characterization

Two different types of coils have been manufactured: (i) a conventional PCB RC with no distributed damping at all, to be used as a reference result and shown in Fig. 6, and (ii) various PCB RCs including the previously discussed distributed damping network at both the inner and outer radii, as shown in Fig. 7.

For the latter case, a large number of samples, each with a different value of R_{damp} , were manufactured. All resistors came in a 0603 metric package with a $\pm 1\%$ tolerance. Their parasitic elements are expected to have a minimal effect below approximately 400 MHz and are thus not considered. As can be seen in Fig. 7, in order to fulfill the component placement constraints of the PCB manufacturer, the inner damping resistors had to be staggered over successive turns. This small placement error is ignored in later simulations.

All test coils were manufactured using two-layer PCBs with a nominal thickness of 1.6 mm, an inner radius of 5 mm, an outer radius of 15 mm and 50 turns in total. Both radii have a negligibly low manufacturing tolerance; the board thickness however has a specified $\pm 10\%$ typical variability, which must be considered when interpreting certain results later on. Finally, in order to reduce errors in later measurements due to changing eccentricity conditions, the radius of the physical orifice of the PCB is reduced as much as possible to ensure a tight fit of the central conductor.

Fig. 6. Prototype PCB RC without any distributed damping network, before and after manually adding the top and bottom shields.

The top and bottom shields were added later using one-sided copper tape with a non-conductive glue layer on both faces of the coil. These are tied to ground through a low impedance connection using the included pads on the PCBs. No return winding was included to simplify the modeling and

Fig. 7. Prototype PCB RC with the complete distributed damping network, before and after manually adding the top and bottom shields.

measurement as much as possible. The copper tape over the entire inner circumference where the primary conductor is meant to be placed is removed afterwards using a scalpel, with care to not create a shorted turn. The trace widths of the coil traces (0.5 mm) were chosen to approximate as closely as possible the characteristic impedance of the VNA used for the measurements ($Z_0 = 50\ \Omega$) with the thickness of the isolating glue layer of the copper tape specified in its datasheet.

Since however neither the exact thickness of the copper tape nor the dielectric constant of its adhesive was known with certainty, the impedance of the reference coil was measured with a Keysight P9374A VNA (also used for all later measurements). The result is shown in Fig. 8. Using both the slope of the curve at the lowest frequencies and the position of the first $\lambda/4$ peak, the total inductance and capacitance of the coil can be estimated to be $L_{coil} = 891\text{ nH}$ and $C_{coil} = 384\text{ pF}$. These values are then used to calculate the pul parameters L' and C' inserted in the models described in Section II.

Fig. 8. Measured impedance of the reference coil without any distributed damping shown in Fig. 6.

The characteristic impedance of the coil is then $Z_0 = \sqrt{L_{coil}/C_{coil}} \approx 48\ \Omega$, in good agreement with the desired value. Results using this prototyping technique have proven to be highly repeatable, as long as the same copper tape is used and care is taken when placing the shields to not leave any air pockets below or above the traces. In comparison to directly manufacturing the sensors

using four-layer PCBs and blind vias, this method has clear advantages in terms of cost and versatility during prototyping. To verify the modeling framework and general effectiveness of the distributed damping network under different load terminations, the simple circuit shown in Fig. 9 was implemented on all coils. To further reduce capacitive coupling at the highest frequencies, the shields are extended to also cover this matching network. In order to avoid perforation of the isolating glue layer of the copper tape by the manually soldered matching resistors, a small piece of electrical tape protected only this small region of the board.

Fig. 9. Schematic implemented in the test coils to test them under different terminating impedance.

B. Test fixture

The test fixture employed for evaluating the Z_T of all the coils shown consists of a single cylindrical conductor placed over a ground plane, and was designed based on existing fixtures for calibrating commercial, high-frequency current probes [33], [34]. It is shown in Fig. 10, and its dimensions are listed in Table I.

Fig. 10. Picture of the employed test fixture with the 50Ω termination inserted. Modeled return current paths shown in red are included in the simulations described in Section II-A. Marked dimensions are shown in Table I; only physical dimensions not marked are the thickness t of the stainless steel plates and the radius of the central wire r_w .

The dashed red arrows indicate the primary current paths considered in the complete simulations described in Section II-A; these paths are approximated based on the expected high-frequency current distribution due to the skin effect, which concentrates currents near the periphery of the conducting surfaces. While at lower frequencies the current paths will be uniform and thus markedly different, their effect on Z_T at these frequencies where TL effects of the sensor are negligible is expected to only change M in a minimal way. At the 50Ω termination, currents are assumed to split uniformly to each side due to the symmetry of the structure.

TABLE I
DIMENSIONS OF THE TEST FIXTURE.

w	\mathcal{L}	h	t	r_w
4 cm	11.5 cm	4 cm	1 mm	0.565 mm

The measured transmission coefficient of the empty fixture S_{12}^{TF} is shown in Fig. 11. Using these values, together with S_{11}^{TF} , the complex propagation constant of the fixture is calculated using the procedure described in [35]. It is found that the fixture introduces a non-negligible loss and distortion above 200 MHz, which sets the absolute upper frequency limit for this setup. Below this frequency, no appreciable difference in S_{12}^{TF} was observed when any of the test coils were inserted, and thus no additional corrections for their loading are needed [36].

Fig. 11. Measured S_{12}^{TF} of the empty test fixture.

The Z_T of any of the sensors discussed before is measured directly using the VNA and the described test fixture. Port 1 of the former is connected to the fixture input, while the opposite end of the fixture is terminated in 50Ω , thus generating the desired known high-frequency current. Port 2 is connected to the coil output, and S_{12}^{Coil} is recorded, measuring the voltage produced by the sensor in response to the known primary current. The measured response is then de-embedded using (6) to correct for the mismatch of the fixture, following the procedure described in [37].

$$Z_T = 50 \Omega \frac{S_{12}^{Coil}}{S_{12}^{TF}} \quad (6)$$

IV. DESIGN OPTIMIZATION AND EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

In this section, the design of the distributed damping network for a typical sensor is described. More specifically, the test coil shown in Fig. 7 was analyzed employing the numerical methods proposed in Section II and their predictions were compared with measurements taken as described in Section III. This process is repeated for two different termination impedance values, so that the conventional coil is operating either in the critically-damped or self-integrating [38] regime.

A. Critically damped termination

Under this condition, one end of the coil is short-circuited $R_{\text{left}} = 0 \Omega$, while at the other end where the output voltage is recorded $R_{\text{L}} = Z_0$ is fulfilled. Due to Z_0 being sufficiently close to 50Ω , the coil was connected directly to the VNA (from Fig. 9, $R_{\text{right}_1} = 0 \Omega$ and R_{right_2} was left open).

For all simulations that follow, the pul L' and C' extracted from the impedance measurements described in Section III-A are used.

Firstly, the simplest model described in Section II-B is employed to predict the relative behavior of Z_T for a wide range of R_{damp} values. The resulting transfer functions are shown in Fig. 12, from which the best value of R_{damp} can be found as the one which results in the flattest response. For values too high ($R_{\text{damp}} > 100 \Omega$), the distributed damping network has no effect, and the original resonances of the sensor at multiples of approximately 30 MHz can be seen. For values too low ($R_{\text{damp}} < 0.5 \Omega$), new resonances originating from the highly mismatched termination of individual PCB traces appear, alongside a drastically reduced gain at lower frequencies which is highly undesirable. Between both regions however, a stable valley centered around $R_{\text{damp}} \approx 1 \Omega$ is present, at which a flat response extending almost to 80 MHz is obtained with essentially no change in the low-frequency gain of the sensor.

With an initial range of suitable values for R_{damp} defined, a smaller set of coils within this range are simulated using the complete method presented in Section II-A and subsequently measured experimentally applying the procedure described in Section III to verify the accuracy of the entire process. For all measurements that follow, the sensors were positioned at the center of the test fixture and aligned parallel to the side plates. The resulting comparison between experimental results and predicted transfer functions is shown in Fig. 13.

Overall, the agreement between the theoretical and measured transfer impedance is excellent. At higher frequencies, the largest discrepancies appear for the undamped coil, whose resonance frequencies are slightly shifted, due to their aforementioned dependence on the positioning of the sensor, and the resonance depths are overestimated, because additional loss mechanisms are neglected in the model.

The upper frequency of the measurement is determined not only by the considerations present in Section III-B but also by residual capacitive coupling, which, despite the shielding introduced, must be considered as an error source above

Fig. 12. Transfer functions obtained using the method presented in Section II-B for different values of $R_{\text{L}} = Z_0$.

Fig. 13. Solid lines show the measured transfer impedance of the test coils for various values of R_{damp} and $R_{\text{L}} = 50 \Omega \approx Z_0$. Dotted lines of the same colors represent the corresponding simulation results, obtained using the procedures described in Section II-A and the pul parameters extracted for the undamped coil.

150 MHz. This limit is obtained to a first approximation by considering the frequency at which the difference between the measured S_{12}^{Coil} with the test fixture terminated in 50Ω and in an open circuit decreases below 5 dB. This threshold was employed because an open termination removes most current from the test fixture (the current is removed entirely for frequencies at which the test fixture is electrically short, and forms a lower amplitude standing wave above this point), eliminating inductive coupling and leaving primarily capacitive feed-through.

While this technique is suitable to estimate above which frequency capacitive coupling becomes relevant, no simple equivalent modeling for this phenomena can be undertaken. Just like the desired inductive coupling, capacitive coupling is a distributed phenomena, and thus at the high-frequencies

of interest can not be represented adequately by lumped components [6]. Furthermore, due to the presence of the dielectric, no analytical expressions can be used to determine the partial potential coefficients between the primary structure and the sensor, and a full meshing of the structure (including the dielectric) would be needed to make a prior estimate of the magnitude of this effect.

Based on the results of Fig. 13, Table II is compiled. The specified transfer impedance Z_T is given for the frequency range comprised between the -3 dB low frequency point $f_{-3\text{dB}}^{\text{LF}}$ and the -3 dB high frequency point $f_{-3\text{dB}}^{\text{HF}}$, where it is approximately flat. For most damping values, this specified value is simply the maximum Z_T within this interval. For $R_{\text{damp}} = 0.1 \Omega$ and especially 0.5Ω , however, a small amount of peaking extends the sensor's bandwidth. Finally, no Z_T is specified for the undamped coil, as its response remains derivative over the entire frequency range of interest.

TABLE II
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MEASURED TEST COILS.

$R_{\text{damp}} [\Omega]$	$Z_T [\text{dB}\Omega]$	$f_{-3\text{dB}}^{\text{LF}} [\text{MHz}]$	$f_{-3\text{dB}}^{\text{HF}} [\text{MHz}]$
0.1	-25	1.5	10.86
0.5	-13	3	> 100
1	-9.72	3.70	65.86
2	-6.35	4.60	46.45
5	-3.85	5.50	29.00
None	-	-	20.62

While the maximally flat response is obtained with $R_{\text{damp}} = 1 \Omega$ as was originally predicted in Fig. 12, to realize the largest possible improvement in bandwidth a value of $R_{\text{damp}} = 0.5 \Omega$ could be used at the cost of only a small amount of peaking. In both cases, bandwidth improvements of factors of slightly more than three and five times over the bandwidth of the original sensor are obtained. For larger values of R_{damp} , the damping becomes progressively less effective, whereas for smaller values Z_T decreases drastically and resonances once again become significant, both conclusions originally reached using only Fig. 12.

Finally, it must be verified that these bandwidth improvements do not come at the expense of the sensor's low-frequency gain, so that the noise-floor of the entire system remains mostly unchanged. The total mutual inductance M of each coil is obtained from the measured value of Z_T at the lowest possible frequency as:

$$M = \frac{|Z_T|(f = 300 \text{ kHz})}{2\pi \cdot 300 \text{ kHz}}. \quad (7)$$

As predicted by Fig. 12, with the exception of $R_{\text{damp}} = 0.1 \Omega$, all estimated values are consistent with that of the reference coil without the damping network, and within the uncertainty associated with the variability in coil height, which directly affects M . The preservation of the total M even after the sensor bandwidth has been extended directly improves the noise performance of a complete measurement system implementing this technique, which is particularly important

at low frequencies where its flicker noise becomes dominant [13].

B. Self-integrating termination

In the previous section, it was seen that the introduction of the distributed damping network in a critically damped coil creates a flat region in its transfer impedance, which must be accounted for by introducing a zero at $f_{-3\text{dB}}^{\text{LF}}$ in the employed integrator. The advantages of this topology have been discussed before in the literature [39], and most significantly include a more relaxed high-frequency and slew-rate requirements for the integrator, since its gain above $f_{-3\text{dB}}^{\text{LF}}$ need only remain at unity and not increase at the previous $+20$ dB/dc. In some applications where mostly the high-frequency performance is of interest, it might be desirable to extend this flat region as much as possible. To achieve this, a self-integrating coil with $R_L < Z_0$ can be employed. Two R_{damp} optimization examples created using the method described in Section II-B for different ratios of R_L/Z_0 are shown in Fig. 14 and 15.

In both cases, the range of R_{damp} values that yield an acceptably flat transfer function becomes wider. However, extending this region over a larger frequency band necessarily results in a lower Z_T .

Additionally, the optimum value for R_{damp} depends on the chosen R_L ; for lower terminating resistances, larger values of R_{damp} are required. Defining the optimum as the value of R_{damp} that yields the flattest possible Z_T transfer function (and thus disregarding any further bandwidth enhancement due to peaking), for different R_L/Z_0 ratios the Z_T of the sensor was simulated for 180 uniformly distributed values of R_{damp} in the 0.75Ω to 2.5Ω range, as described in Section II-B, obtaining Fig. 16 as a result. It can be seen how the latter significantly influences the appropriate choice of R_{damp} .

Fig. 14. Transfer functions obtained using the method presented in Section II-B for different values of R_{damp} and $R_L = 0.1Z_0$.

Fig. 15. Transfer functions obtained using the method presented in Section II-B for different values of R_{damp} and $R_L = 0.01Z_0$.

Fig. 16. Values of R_{damp} needed to obtain the flattest Z_T for descending values of the R_L/Z_0 ratio, obtained with the method shown in Section II-B.

Finally, because of the concentrated nature of the induced voltage in PCB RCs, resonant peaks still appear for self-integrating conventional coils, even for a very long, centered and collinear primary conductor. The proposed distributed damping network, however, largely suppresses these peaks.

In order to perform an initial verification of the modeling framework for this type of termination impedance, some of the previously discussed test coils had their matching networks shown in Fig. 9 modified to include $R_{\text{right}_2} = 13 \Omega$, and thus obtain $R_L = 13 \Omega \parallel 50 \Omega \approx 10 \Omega$, as simulated in Fig. 14. No lower values for R_L were tested due to the limited usefulness of a probe with such a significantly reduced Z_T .

The comparison between the measured and the simulated Z_T is shown in Fig. 17. The relatively poor agreement for the undamped case is unsurprising, not only because of the unconsidered loss mechanisms smoothing various resonant

Fig. 17. Solid lines show the measured transfer impedance of the test coils for various values of R_{damp} and $R_L = 10 \Omega \approx 0.1Z_0$. Dotted lines of the same colors represent the corresponding simulation results, obtained using the procedures described in Section II-A and the pul parameters extracted for the undamped coil.

peaks, but more significantly due to their strong dependence on even small changes of the position of the coil inside the test fixture. In contrast, no such variation has been observed for any of the sensors including a distributed damping network, whose agreement with simulated values remains good. The slight underestimation of Z_T at low frequencies is attributed to the previously discussed variability in M as a result of manufacturing spread on the board thickness, which in any case would be corrected in later calibrations of the probe.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a distributed damping network capable of significantly expanding the bandwidth of PCB RCs without affecting their low-frequency gain has been presented. In comparison to existing bandwidth extension techniques, no change to the mechanical structure of the sensor or additional conditioning circuits are needed, adding only two additional resistors for each turn.

Because the focus of this paper is on the proposed technique itself, the fabricated prototypes are intended solely for its validation rather than as fully optimized, standalone sensors. Nevertheless, they demonstrate an improved sensitivity–bandwidth trade-off compared to existing PCB Rogowski coils. This improvement is illustrated in Table III, where a literature review originally presented in [40] is extended with the results of this work, together with the product of each coil’s low-frequency sensitivity and bandwidth. The latter serves as a figure of merit to evaluate the tradeoff between both parameters as presented in the Introduction. It should be noted that, unlike most reported works, the bandwidth in this study is defined and evaluated in the frequency domain while explicitly accounting for capacitive coupling effects, which are typically not considered in reported bandwidth figures and can significantly limit the high-frequency response.

TABLE III
EXPANDED LITERATURE COMPARISON FROM [40].

Source	M [nH]	Shielding	BW [MHz]	$M \cdot BW$ [nH·MHz]
[41]	1.71	No	115.9	198
[42]	2.54	Yes	42.8	109
[43]	2.54	No	28.3	71.9
[44]	11.13	No	13.8	153
[40]	5.64	Yes	≈ 300	1692
This work	14.88	Yes	$> 100^1$	> 1600

¹ Limited by capacitive coupling, not measured in the frequency domain in any other reference.

Motivated by the complexity of the equivalent circuit of a sensor equipped with the proposed network, two numerical methods have been developed. These methods enable the efficient design of distributively damped PCB RCs, requiring only a minimal number of experimental measurements and achieving over an order of magnitude smaller iteration times than full-wave solvers. The accuracy and suitability of both methods have been verified by an extensive set of measurements employing a dedicated high-frequency test fixture. Finally, the effectiveness of the distributed damping network has been demonstrated in both critically-damped and self-integrating coils. The latter requires a more precise determination of R_{damp} but can achieve a slightly larger Z_T , while the former tolerates a less precise selection of R_{damp} and extends the flat Z_T region at the expense of a slightly reduced transfer impedance.

Future work will focus on developing methods to predict capacitive coupling for typical shielding structures without requiring full discretization of the sensor dielectric, thereby avoiding the associated increase in simulation time and computational cost. Preliminary simulations indicate that overcoming this limitation would enable further improvements in bandwidth through more complex distributed damping networks.

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